

The Worth of Extrinsic and Intrinsic Reward among College Staff of Khairpur Sindh Pakistan.

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ABSTRACT

There is a great impact of employee's motivation on their job performance. It is because when employees feel great motivation toward their job then they perform more effectively and efficiently. Education sector plays very vital role in any economy and believe that development of economy is also depend upon its performance so it's very important thing that employees of education sector must be satisfied and highly motivated toward their job in order to enhance the efficiency of this sector for the development of country. This research is conduct to know the worth of current reward intrinsic and extrinsic on motivation of employees among teaching staff of khairpur. The purpose of this study is to know how well the current reward system of Government College helps to generate the employee's motivation toward their jobs The qualitative research design was used in this work. The data was collected through interview and survey which was analyzed with help of Nvivo 10. In this, nodes were formed and data was coded. After that matrix coding query is run for getting result. Matrix coding query gives the results .After analysis the conclusion is that the teaching staff of government college of khairpur is highly motivated toward their job because of current reward practice of the organization .

Key words: Job motivation, Reward system

1: INTRODUCTION

To face this challenging economy successfully it's very necessary for the organization that their Human capital must be motivated toward their job .Organization try to provide that type of environment in which employees feel satisfaction and motivation toward their job. Many organizations provide a very large number of intrinsic and extrinsic reward in order to develop the employee holding and motivation .there by increasing the organizational productivity. (Neelkamal, 2012)

Reward system can be defined as the set of the values that bidding the values toward employees .It is a general thought that people are the only scare resource of the organization which cannot be easily imitated by other organization based on this point of view investment on employees should be of high importance for the organization .The main objective of reward system is to motivate the employees for the work they do and to attract new employees .It looks very difficult to determine which are the best practices of reward system . (laakso, 2012)

Extrinsic reward can be defined as non job related reward such as pay salary etc.It is said that finance matters for all of us and it motivate us because of its value. Money motivates us as long as we get another pay increase. Extrinsic reward is best practices when we want to motivate the employees. (Armstrong, Brown, & Reilly, 2010)

Intrinsic reward can be defined as reward that are job inherent non financial rewards including challenging and interesting job and training for employees .Most common and effective intrinsic reward practice is praise and recognition. (laakso, 2012) Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation can be defined as the motivation developing by giving intrinsic and extrinsic reward and through this making employees feel important in the organization .Training of employees appropriately, developing the carrier plan with employees and make them motivated toward their job (oudejans, 2007)

1.1 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Following are two questions of research that were investigated.

- What are the current reward practices in colleges of khairpur?
- At what extent the current rewards have the impact on employees' motivation?

2: LITERATURE REVIEW

(Njanja1, 2013) Reward management is one of the method used by companies for attracting and holding their human capital as well as promoting them to improve their performance. a firm that deals with financial services delivered superior performance and took care of it.

(Neelkamal, 2012) suggest that the reward system is the source of motivation for the employees of organization and not only this but it also help to achieve the

organizational objective .it is a very big deal for every organization that which type of reward system can motivate the employees more but most of the organization applying a mixture of both financial and non financial reward in order to satisfy the need of the employees. The reward access can only be expand by organization if they understand the need of the employees based on knowing the preferences of human capital. It is suggest that a new reward system must be prepared to incorporate the reward choice and assumptions of both the employees and the organization although taking into the accounts that impact the outside environment ,the job layout and the connection between the desire from the organization and the employee of organization .

(Finkle, 2011) Organization use money to reward their human capital performance during the year under appraisal. But there is also the expectation that this money will be a factor in motivating employees' performance next year's well. Employees who get a large monetary reward will likely want to get it next year too. On the other side employees who receive a miserly bonus and it shows how the organization assessed their performance, might

Consider improving next year

(purkayastha, 2011) Employees even in the turbulent environment that had gripped the entire financial services industry. The firm had given good performance and industry observers felt that its performance management and reward system was Responsible for this.

(Armstrong, Brown, & Reilly, 2010) Described that organization allocate a huge amount for reward system .The main objective behind this is only to motivate, hold, effectuate and appeal to new employees.

(Mikander, 2010) State that the motivation of employees is a very basic thing for the organizational performance and for that it is the today's requirements that the organization must develop the proper reward system that encourage and enhance the capabilities of the employees for better performance toward their work which has ultimately effect on organization's performance. A proper combination of intrinsic and extrinsic reward can

upgrade the motivation of employees toward the work performance and their loyalty toward the organization.

(Torrington, Derek, Taylor, & Stephen, 2009)Described that motivation is the aspiration to get above assumptions, stimulate with the help of internal factor as compare to external factor.

(Anna & Sandra, 2009)States that reward system is the method by which employees are able to motivate to participate in the organization performance .It is very necessary that reward system must exist at all levels of the management so at each and every level all employees become motivated toward their work.

(Brown, 2008)Researched that in many organization most of the reward practice are in use because in many other organization same practice are in use so they follow the same practice and this is only for that because there is lack of information or there is limited management resources.

(Manopoulous, 2008) suggest that there are two kind of reward system that influence the employees motivation at work ,financial and non financial ,non financial are the factors such as work recognition, training .opportunity for advancement, vacations, tickets for entertainment means it include all the thing which not contain the money .

3:Theoretical Framework

In this study Maslow's hierarchy of needs and goal setting theory is used in order to investigate the impact of reward system on teachers in Government College of khairpur.

Maslow's suggest that people are motivated to satisfy need .According to Maslow people always want what they do not yet have .Maslow splits human needs into five levels namely Physiological need, safety needs ,social needs ,esteem needs and self actualization needs . (H & Stephen, 1998) Organization must appreciate all the requirement and needs of their employees in order to motivate them because when employees feel that their all need become satisfied then they motivate toward their job.

3.1 Research model

3.2 Research Hypothesis

H: There is a positive impact of current reward practices of Government College on the motivation of their teaching staff

4: METHODOLOGY

The qualitative research methodology was used in this study.

4.1 Sample of Study

A sample of study was lecturer of Government College.

4.2 Data Collection Techniques

Data was collected via interviews and survey from lecturer of Government College of khairpur

The structured questionnaires were used in survey. The questions of reward system was taken from the article of (laakso, 2012). The reliability of instrument was checked via SPSS 16.

4.3 Data Analyze Technique

Due to qualitative nature of research, the NVivo 10 software was used in this study. The NVivo 10 converts unorganized data into organized form via nodes and coding of data.

4.4 Nodes and Coding

In NVivo, nodes were formed and data were coded in their respective nodes. In this paper main nodes are current reward practices, motivation, relationship between intrinsic and extrinsic reward ,and future development.

5: FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Queries

The three queries of NVivo 10 was run in order to get results. Three queries were Word Frequency Query, Text Search Query and Matrix Coding Query.

5.2 Word Frequency Query

The word frequency query was run in order to see which word was frequently use in nodes. The findings showed that the words reward, performance.motivation were frequently used by respondents. The word cloud of word frequency query is shown in appendix

5.3 Text Search Query

The text search query was run in order to see the link between different sentences over one word. The text search query was run on reward system themes. The tree map of text search query of themes is shown in appendix.

5.4 Matrix Coding Query

The proposed hypothesis was tested by applying Matrix Coding Query.

H1:, There is a positive impact of current reward practices of Government College on the motivation of their teaching staff

After testing the hypothesis the conclusion is that there is a positive effect of current reward system of Government College of khairpur on the motivation of teaching staff .The Node matrix result is shown in appendix.

6: LIMITATION

In this research paper the limitation is that it's only give the information of role of motivation among academic staff of educational institutions of Khairpur Pakistan only. The further study can be taken through increasing the size of sample and target area.

7: REFERENCES

- Anna, A., & Sandra, B. (2009). *Reward system motivating different generation* . Gothenburg : school of economics business and law .
- Armstrong, Brown, & Reilly. (2010). creating measurable business impact . *Evidence -based reward management* .
- Armstrong, Brown, & Reilly. (2010). *Evidence based reward management* . london: kogan page ltd.
- Brown. (2008). Measuring the effectiveness of pay and reward . *compensation and benefits review* , 23-41.
- Finkle. (2011). <http://ezinearticles.com>.
- H, M. A., & Stephen. (1998). *Maslow on management* . New York .
- laakso, L. (2012). *The impact of financial and non financial reward on employees motivation* . Turkey : university of applied.
- Manopoulous. (2008). An evaluation of employee motivation in the extended public sector . *Employees relations* , 63-85.
- Mikander, C. (2010). *The impact of a reward sytem on employee*. Finland: ARCADA.
- Neelkamal. (2012). *comparing the impact of monetary and non moetary reward toward employees and organization motivation* . Gordon : university of pretoria.
- Neelkamal. (2012). *comparing the impact of monetary and non monetary reward programmes toward employees motivation* . pretoria.
- Njanja1, W. L. (2013). Effect of Reward on Employee Performance: A Case of Kenya Power. *International Journal of Business and Management* , 41-49.
- oudejans. (2007). *linking intrinsic and extrinsic reward* .
- purkayastha. (2011). www.ecch.com/educators/product/.
- Torrington, Derek, Taylor, & Stephen. (2009). Fundamental of Human Resource managent. *Persons education limited* , 439.

APPENDIX

WORD CLOUD OF WORD FREQUENCY QUERY

HYPOTHESIS 1: NODE MATRIX OF MATRIX CODING QUERY

